

ISic0941

I.Sicily inscription 0941

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

natural rock

Object

painted rock face

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Catacomba di San Giovanni

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Εὐμοίρει

2. Θεοκτίστην

1. Οὐλπία δέξε

2. τεκοῦσα Θεοκτίστην

3. λαγόνεσ[σι]ν

1. Εὐμοίρει [Οὐλπία]

Apparatus

Text after IG, with slight changes

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492571

EDCS 39102098

PHI 140422

PHI 333255

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0941. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4340138>